

06 On Discrete Euclidean Space

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The paper is the sixth post of the blog “Discrete Euclidean Space” at <https://www.conceptualframeworks.org>.

The post is about the topological deformation of the deformable part of the units of the structure of discrete space.

The topological volume

The volume of the inscribed sphere of each unit of discrete space in vacuum space is $\approx 74\%$ of the whole volume of the unit. In vacuum space every scalar of the units has the same magnitude and represents the static part of the units.

figure 1

The remaining part of the unit is the dynamical part of its volume. Because the scalar mechanism of every unit tries to expand the inscribed sphere until the whole volume of the unit is a sphere. Both volumes are visible in figure 1, an *imaginary* symmetrical unit (rhombic dodecahedron).

All the units have identical basic properties and all the units tessellate our universe. The consequence is that the units transform their shapes synchronously and in a smooth way although the synchronisation is the cause behind the existence of a fixed amount of topological deformation between all the units. A universal periodic switch of the direction of the transfer of topological deformation between the joint faces of the units (figure 2 in post **04**).

In physics this fixed amount of topological deformation is the quantum of energy, Planck’s constant (h). However, our universe is non-local and it means that everything influences everything at exactly the same moment. That is why

it is not totally granted that the amount of topological deformation of the quantum is always the same during the whole evolution of the universe. Is it possible to prove that the fixed amount of energy of the quantum will always be the same?

Time represents the continues and synchronized “flow” of change of the deformable part of all the units of discrete space. The cause behind the topological deformations is the internal spherical shape forming mechanism of every unit, the scalar mechanism. Changes of the “dynamical power” of the scalar mechanism don’t influence the *mutual relations* between all the units of discrete space. On the other hand, the volume of every unit of discrete space is invariant and every unit has the same basic properties. Therefore it is really awkward to propose that the fixed amount of energy of the quantum can change during the evolution of the universe.

There is another important question to solve, where do units transform their shapes? It is clear that the transformation of the shape of a unit is related to the transitional area between the surface of the inscribed sphere – the scalar of the Higgs field – and the deformed part of the unit.

Figure 1 in **05** was constructed with the help of concentric shells of a sphere. I can use this model to examine the deformation of the joint face between 2 adjacent units (figure 2). The image shows that to expand the undistorted scalar mechanism the unit has to transfer volume to the points of contact between the scalars to add the first incomplete shell (blue) to the volume of the scalar. There is no logic to assume that the transfer will happen at A or at B.

figure 2

Not all the units in discrete space have the same amount of topological deformation. That means that the mutual relations between units has differentiate. But a differentiation between deformed volumes and surface areas will violate the proposed identical “power” of all the units in discrete space to change their shape. Figure 3 shows the problem.

figure 3

The schematic unit in the centre of figure 3 is deformed by the unit at the right and is the cause of the deformation of the unit at the left, because $\Delta V_{input} = \Delta V_{output}$. The result of the deformation is the change at the surface area of the units. A part of the scalar of the unit in the centre has become a part of the boundary of the whole unit because of Δv_{input} (green arrow). However, the deformation of the shape of the unit in the centre has not increased or decreased the volume and surface area of the deformed part of the unit (white). And it doesn't matter if the deformation of 1 quantum is between 2 faces of the unit or between all the faces.

Figure 3 shows that the “power” behind the topological deformation is identical for every unit of discrete space, even if the scalar decreases its radius, because $\Delta V_{input} = \Delta V_{output}$. Comparable with the conservation during the transfer of 1 quantum of topological deformation by every unit of discrete space during the constant of time, $1 t_c$ (03, page 2).

Fields

The transfer of volume to the joint face by the unit at the right side to the unit in the centre results in a disruption of the symmetry of the scalar vectors of the unit in the centre. Because the deformed volume of the unit at the right affects the surface of the scalar of the unit in the centre in a direct way.

So we have to conclude that the transfer of a quantum – Planck's constant – corresponds with the increase or decrease of a scalar vector. Just what the corresponding electric and magnetic fields are supposed to do. The electric field transfers energy with the speed of light and the mag-

netic field – a vector field – determines the direction of the amplitudes of the electric field. Because in vacuum space every scalar has 12 vectors inside because of the 12 points of contact with the adjacent units around (see 05, figure 4).

Figure 4 is like figure 1, except the scalar vectors between the 12 points of contact. The image gives an impression of the continuous existence of these scalar vectors within vacuum space. The deformation of every face of a unit is constantly changing thus de distinct scalar vector is changing too. In other words, within vacuum space every scalar is constantly influenced by the scalar vectors of all the other units in the universe. Vectors don't transfer energy so there is no restriction to the velocity of the influence of the scalar vectors. Vectors act instantaneous and that is the origin of the observed non-locality of our universe (see 04).

I can describe the volume of a unit of discrete space with the help of 2 different concepts. The concept that a part of the volume is static and represents the inscribed sphere inside the whole volume of the unit – created by the undistorted part of the scalar mechanism – and the remaining dynamical part of the volume that is responsible for all the changes in the universe.

figure 4

If I change concepts I can describe the undistorted part of the scalar mechanism as the scalar of the Higgs field, because the Higgs field exists everywhere in the universe. All the dynamical parts of the units form the electric field. A topological field – known as *waves* or *amplitudes* – that is responsible for the mutual exchange of fixed amounts of energy, the quantum (Planck's constant). The magnetic field is a vector field and vectors need a rigid medium to be transferred through.

The magnitudes of the scalars of the Higgs field are decreased inside a Black hole because of the enormous concentration of quanta (topological deformation). However, the vectors of the magnetic field in vacuum space are the

result of the flat Higgs field; every scalar has the same magnitude and together the scalars form a rigid medium for the vectors. That is why there cannot exist a magnetic field inside a Black hole. The deformation of the electric field inside a Black hole is enormous in comparison to vacuum space. Thus if the electric field and the magnetic field are still corresponding fields inside a black hole we must observe an enormous magnetic field around the rotating Black hole. But that's not exactly what we observe.^[1]

In other words, the conclusion that the amplitudes of the electric field create corresponding vectors inside the scalars of the flat Higgs field is a convincing concept about the origin of the magnetic field.

Despite of the simplicity and mathematical consistency of the description about the properties of the universal fields in space, the description of origin and the properties of the gravitational field are still missing.

References:

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